

Relation between the paper “*Lessons Learned from Developing a Sustainability Awareness Framework for Software Engineering using Design Science*” and previous works of its authors.

The aforementioned paper describes years of work on the development and validation of the Sustainability Awareness Framework (SusAF). Its aim is to discuss the systematic development, using design science, of a sustainability tool for the development and analysis of software systems.

As it could not be different, the present paper builds on and refers to work published in the past, as well as presents several new data points, new theoretical background, and new lessons learned.

The aim of the present work is completely different from the previous ones --- *to share our experience in tool design with other software engineering researchers* --- and its contribution **could not have been deducted** from reading all our previous papers. In Table 1, we describe in detail all our previous papers that relate to SusAF.

Table 1: Relation to previous works by authors and others

Previous work	Relation to present paper
<p><i>Chitchyan, R., Becker, C., Betz, S., Duboc, L., Penzenstadler, B., Seyff, N., & Venters, C. C. (2016, May). Sustainability design in requirements engineering: state of practice. In Proceedings of the 38th International Conference on Software Engineering Companion (pp. 533-542).</i></p>	<p>This previous work related to the Cycle 1, as it discusses the foundational study that motivated the SusAF development. It consists of interviews with RE practitioners about their perceptions, practices, and challenges in addressing sustainability in their professional activities.</p> <p>The results, detailed in 6 pages, highlight the lack of knowledge, support, and sense of responsibility perceived by requirements engineers. The authors make a series of recommendations, among which is the integration of sustainability into RE practice and training at all levels.</p> <p>Conversely, the present paper summarizes in 1/2 a page the main findings of this original study, illustrating with a quote of one study participant, which was <u>not</u> used in the previous paper.</p> <p>The overall lesson learned presented in this cycle is the need for methods, guidelines and tools to consider the sustainability effects of software systems. This is different but, naturally, derived from the conclusion referred above.</p> <p>Furthermore, the present paper discusses the implication of this lesson learned to SE research, education, and practice. More specifically, it details the kind of tools required, the fact the university curriculum needs to be adapted, and sustainability needs to be integrated into the software development process.</p>
<p><i>Penzenstadler, B., Betz, S., Venters, C. C., Chitchyan, R., Porras, J., Seyff, N., ... & Becker, C. (2018, May). Everything is INTERRELATED: teaching software engineering for</i></p>	<p>This previous work relates with the cycles 2 and 3 of the present paper. That work described our experience with a week-long course on sustainability and requirements engineering with 13 LUT students, where several teaching artifacts were used.</p> <p>The Sustainability Awareness Diagram (SusAD), not the framework, was one of the 20 activities performed by students during that week. The paper did not describe the artifacts themselves or their development. It just mentioned its use and showed an example.</p>

<p><i>sustainability. In Proceedings of the 40th International Conference on Software Engineering: Software Engineering Education and Training (pp. 153-162).</i></p>	<p>Furthermore, the previous paper discussed the survey filled out by students regarding the whole course, and the lessons learned referred to the general challenge of teaching sustainability to computer science students.</p> <p>Conversely, in the present paper, Cycle 2 describes the state-of-the-art and the development of that artifact (SusAD), which was not discussed at all in the previous paper. Furthermore, the 13 students from LUT represented only one of the three data points described in the cycle 3 of this paper. Additionally, the quotes used in the previous paper were from the other two datasets not reported in the previous paper.</p> <p>The aggregated results of the three datasets were discussed in a summarized form and the lessons learned were about the need for dimension and temporal thinking in SusAD. The implications of this lesson learned to SE research, education, and practice related to the need to assess the impact of IT products, to include system thinking into SE courses, and to relate software development to corporate sustainability reporting. Neither the lessons learned nor the implications were discussed in the previous paper.</p>
<p><i>L. Duboc et al., "Do we Really Know What we are Building? Raising Awareness of Potential Sustainability Effects of Software Systems in Requirements Engineering," 2019 IEEE 27th International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE), Jeju, Korea (South), 2019, pp. 6-16, doi: 10.1109/RE.2019.00013</i></p>	<p>This previous work relates to the cycles 4 and 5 of the present paper. This previous work describes the questions set of SusAF, how they were developed, and their application to students in Finland and in the US. Each of these elements are explained in detail. For example, the results are presented in three-pages.</p> <p>Despite describing how the question set was developed, that paper did not present explicit lessons learned about its development process. Instead, the focus was on how the SusAF helped students to see beyond the software itself, considering its situated environment, and by doing so, requirements engineers can play an important role in supporting sustainability.</p> <p>Conversely, in the present paper, Cycle 4 describes the state-of-the-art behind the development of the questions (not covered in the first paper) and very briefly mentions the methodology that was used.</p> <p>In Cycle 5, the evaluation summarizes in 1/2 page the most interesting insights from three datasets (Finland, US, and Germany), the latter not discussed at all in the previous paper. Finally, the quotes exemplified in this paper have not been quoted in the previous paper.</p> <p>The lessons learned in this paper were, as expected, derived from these experiences. More explicitly, the lesson learned talks about the need for examples to help to understand the impact of software-based systems on the situated environment. This comes from both the ease and the difficulties that students had to apply that version of SusAF.</p> <p>Furthermore, in the implications of this lesson learned to SE research, education, and practice, the present paper identified: the need to develop a pool of examples, the discussion of industrial projects with students, and the importance of knowledge transfer projects to companies. These have not been discussed in the previous paper.</p>
<p><i>Duboc, L., Penzenstadler, B.,</i></p>	<p>This previous work relates to cycles 3, 4, 6 and 7 of the present paper. More precisely, we compared the impressions of the very first set of students using</p>

<p><i>Porras, J., Akinli Kocak, S., Betz, S., Chitchyan, R., ... & Venters, C. C. (2020). Requirements engineering for sustainability: an awareness framework for designing software systems for a better tomorrow. Requirements Engineering, 25, 469-492.</i></p>	<p>SusAF (referred to as baseline), with the impressions from students 2 interactions latter (Cycles 3 and 7), also explaining how the framework evolved in between (Cycles 4 and 6). It is worth noting that these datasets for Cycle 3 were different from the previous papers.</p> <p>The detailed results were presented in 11 pages. The discussion only identified very minor points of improvement (better wording for some questions). The remaining future work does not relate to the present paper.</p> <p>Conversely, the present paper summarizes and extends the data presented in both previous works, adding two new datasets to cycles 3 and 7.</p> <p>There were no lessons learned on cycle 7, as the improvements were too minor to justify a new design cycle.</p>
<p><i>Porras, J., Venters, C. C., Penzenstadler, B., Duboc, L., Betz, S., Seyff, N., ... & Oyediji, S. (2021). How could we have known? Anticipating sustainability effects of a software product. In Software Business: 12th International Conference, ICSOB 2021, Drammen, Norway, December 2–3, 2021, Proceedings 12 (pp. 10-17). Springer International Publishing.</i></p>	<p>This previous paper relates to Cycle 8 of the present paper. More precisely, it concerns 1 of the 3 experiences reported in Cycle 8. This paper was the first to report an application of SusAF in an industrial setting.</p> <p>Its main interest was in describing the actual effects anticipated on the workshops and reflecting on whether SusAF could be related to the company's CSR strategy.</p> <p>Finally, the paper did not discuss the development or the evolution of SusAF.</p> <p>Conversely, the present paper, describes in Cycle 8 our aggregated observations from the application of SusAF to <u>three companies</u>.</p> <p>Unlike the previous paper, it did not present the actual effects anticipated for these systems. Instead, it simply presented quantitative data related to the number of effects and chains of effects.</p> <p>The data reported in the previous paper is summarized in one of the 3 columns of Table 4.</p> <p>The remaining texts, quotes, and examples <u>do not appear</u> in the previous papers.</p> <p>Furthermore, the present paper described the aggregated feedback from workshops' participants and observation from moderators, which was not the aim of the previous paper.</p> <p>With respect to the lessons learned, the current paper discusses the need for guidelines for the application of SusAF without the researchers. This implies the development of guidelines by researchers, the use of examples with multiple levels of complexity to students, and the need for collaboration between different types of profiles in companies. None of these were discussed in the previous paper.</p>